

SITE SPH/INX GS 79	DATE - 5/12/79	AREA E	SQUARE N1/E1	PAGE
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Coordinates:	Levels	
	Top: 10.59 - 10.56	Bottom: 10.26 - 10.20
DIMENSIONS		
Diameter:	Width: 85 cm N-S	Length: Runs under Roman Pavement
		Depth: ≈ 36 cm

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions	
1					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
Other							
2					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
Other							
3					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
Other							
4					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
Other							
5					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
Other							

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/	No./	B&W: Roll/	No./
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DRAWN	Area Plan:	Feature Plan:	Sections:
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: